

Building Change-Ready Organizations: The Critical Role of Self-Efficacy and Adaptability

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Abstract

This article explores the pivotal roles of self-efficacy and adaptability in facilitating successful organizational change. In the contemporary business environment, characterized by rapid technological advancements and market shifts, organizations must remain agile and responsive. Self-efficacy, defined as an individual's belief in their competence, and adaptability, the ability to adjust to new conditions, are critical in overcoming resistance to change and ensuring positive outcomes. The paper discusses how fostering these attributes through targeted interventions such as training programs, leadership development, and supportive organizational cultures can enhance employee readiness and commitment to change. Additionally, the integration of emotional intelligence and resilience into these initiatives further strengthens organizational adaptability. By investing in these areas, organizations can build a workforce capable of navigating change effectively, thus securing a competitive edge in the dynamic business landscape. The article concludes with implications for practice and future research, emphasizing the importance of developing self-efficacy and adaptability to drive successful organizational transformations.

Keywords: Organizational change, Adaptability, Self-efficacy, Change management, Leadership, Emotional intelligence, Resilience, Employee training, Digital transformation, Organizational culture, Transformational leadership, Positive psychology interventions, Psychological empowerment, Collective efficacy, Employee readiness.

1. Introduction

Organizational change is an inevitable aspect of any business, enabling organizations to remain relevant and competitive in today's dynamic and constantly evolving business environment (Cameron & Green, 2015; Hayes, 2018). However, implementing change often encounters

resistance from employees, which can hinder the success of organizational change initiatives (Oreg, Vakola, & Armenakis, 2011). To overcome these obstacles, organizations need to foster a workforce that is both adaptable and self-efficacious (Parker & Collins, 2010).

Adaptability refers to an individual's ability to adjust to changes in their environment, learn from new experiences, and remain resilient in the face of change. Research shows that employees with high levels of adaptability are better equipped to cope with change and are more likely to experience positive outcomes following organizational transitions (Zhou & George, 2001). Additionally, self-efficacy is an individual's belief in their ability to handle challenging, difficult, or new situations with their own competencies. Individuals with high self-efficacy trust in their ability to perform specific tasks or achieve particular goals, recognizing their own effectiveness (Warner, n.d.). Studies have found that employees with high self-efficacy are more likely to embrace change and demonstrate greater commitment to the change process (Chen et al., 2001; Herold et al., 2007).

Given the importance of adaptability and self-efficacy for successful organizational change initiatives, it is crucial for organizations to promote the development of these skills in their employees. This can be achieved through various initiatives such as training and development programs, job rotation opportunities, coaching, and mentoring. By investing in these areas, organizations can create a workforce better equipped to handle the challenges of organizational change and succeed in today's competitive business environment (Breevaart, Bakker, Demerouti, & Derks, 2014; Gong, Huang, & Farth, 2009).

Organizational change encompasses any planned or unplanned shift in an organization's structure, processes, culture, or technology (Cummings & Worley, 2014). These changes may result from external factors, such as shifts in market demand or regulatory changes, or internal factors, such as a desire to improve efficiency or increase innovation. Organizational change can be initiated by various stakeholders, including top management, employees, or external consultants, and can take forms such as mergers and acquisitions, restructurings, or new product launches (Burnes, 2004).

In today's business environment, organizational change is of paramount importance as organizations need to remain agile and responsive to changing market conditions to survive and thrive. Failure to adapt can lead to reduced competitiveness, decreased market share, or even organizational failure. Successful organizational change initiatives can result in increased innovation, improved productivity, enhanced customer satisfaction, and other positive outcomes that contribute to long-term organizational success (Burke, 2017).

However, implementing organizational change is not always straightforward. It requires significant effort and

resources and is often met with resistance from employees who are comfortable with the status quo (Beer & Nohria, 2000). Therefore, organizations must carefully plan and execute change initiatives, involve employees in the process, and provide the necessary support and resources to ensure successful outcomes.

Adaptability and self-efficacy are critical factors in the success of organizational change initiatives (Raffery, Jimmieson, & Armenakis, 2013). Adaptability enables individuals to adjust to changes, learn from new experiences, and remain resilient, which has been positively related to successful organizational change. Adaptable employees are better able to navigate workplace changes, leading to increased job satisfaction and lower stress levels (Oreg & Berson, 2011). Similarly, self-efficacy, the belief in one's ability to perform specific tasks or achieve goals, plays a crucial role. Employees with high self-efficacy are more likely to embrace change and commit to the change process, contributing proactively to organizational change (Bandura et al., 2003).

Recent studies highlight the role of emotional intelligence (EI) and resilience in enhancing self-efficacy and adaptability. Leaders' EI significantly correlates with higher self-efficacy and resilience among employees, fostering a supportive environment for change (Mohamed & Mohamed, 2022). Additionally, organizations undergoing digital transformations face unique challenges that require heightened employee readiness, emphasizing the importance of skills and training in digital competencies (Hutabarat, Devany, & Manurung, 2021).

The purpose of this article is to explore the critical role of self-efficacy and adaptability in building change-ready organizations. It aims to provide insights into how these qualities can be developed and leveraged to overcome resistance to change and ensure the success of organizational change initiatives. This discussion is particularly relevant to current business challenges, as organizations today face unprecedented levels of uncertainty and rapid change due to technological advancements, globalization, and shifting market dynamics. By understanding and fostering adaptability and self-efficacy in their workforce, organizations can better navigate these challenges and secure a competitive advantage.

In conclusion, adaptability and self-efficacy are essential for successful organizational change. Organizations that invest in developing these skills in their employees are more likely to achieve their change goals and navigate the challenges of organizational change effectively. Moreover, incorporating emotional intelligence and resilience into training programs can further enhance employees' readiness

for change, ensuring a smoother transition and greater organizational resilience (Mohamed & Mohamed, 2022; Hutabarat et al., 2021).

2. Self-Efficacy and Organizational Change

Self-efficacy, defined as an individual’s belief in their own competence, plays a crucial role in organizational change. It is the subjective conviction that one can master challenging, difficult, or new situations using their competencies (Warner, n.d.). This awareness of one’s effectiveness is pivotal during organizational change, influencing an individual’s willingness and ability to participate in the change process.

Bandura's social cognitive theory (1992, 1997, 2001) identifies self-efficacy as a primary factor influencing behavior, divided into expectations of competence and consequences. Schwarzer et al. (2002) expanded on Bandura’s work, proposing that generalized self-efficacy is a stable personality trait positively correlated with self-esteem, optimism, and internal control while negatively correlated with anxiety, neuroticism, and depression (Schwarzer, 2014). This trait, part of the HERO resources (Hope, Efficacy, Resilience, Optimism), impacts employee commitment and productivity (Luthans et al., 2004).

Self-efficacy expectations are derived from four main sources: personal experiences, vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion, and physiological and emotional states (Bandura, 1997; Luthans et al., 2004). These sources influence an individual’s perception, evaluation, and regulation of their actions, directly affecting behavior through perseverance, choice, and emotional reactions.

Depiction 1: Handlungstheoretisches Handlungs-Wert-Modell (translated; Schwarzer, 2014, S. 128)

Transformational leadership significantly enhances self-efficacy, as shown in research by Deviana and Hendarsjah (2023), which demonstrates that transformational leadership positively affects cognitive, emotional, and intentional reactions to organizational change, with self-efficacy acting as a mediator. Transformational leaders, by serving as charismatic role models and providing inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, foster an environment where employees feel

more confident and prepared to face organizational changes (Bass, 1985; Podsakoff et al., 1990).

Similarly, Mangundjaya et al. (2023) found that change leadership influences affective commitment to change through self-efficacy. This underscores the importance of leaders who can inspire confidence and resilience in their employees, thus enhancing their commitment to change initiatives. Change leadership, characterized by behaviors such as creating vision, empowering employees, and monitoring progress, directly impacts employees' readiness and emotional responses to change (Mangundjaya, Putri, & Shafira, 2023).

Further studies emphasize the role of self-efficacy in organizational change. Youssef and Luthans (2007) noted that the internalization of behaviors modeled by others can bolster self-efficacy. This is critical during organizational change, where employees must adapt to new roles and expectations. High self-efficacy leads to positive attitudes toward change, reducing resistance and fostering a proactive approach to change implementation.

Depiction 2: Quellen und Veränderungsmöglichkeiten der Selbstwirksamkeitserwartung (translated; Bandura, 1997, S. 477).

The development of self-efficacy in employees can be achieved through targeted interventions such as training programs, mentorship, and opportunities for skill development. These initiatives not only enhance individual competencies but also build a supportive environment that mitigates the fear of failure and promotes resilience (Hutabarat, Devany, & Manurung, 2021). Additionally, psychological empowerment, which includes dimensions such as meaning, competence, self-determination, and impact, plays a critical role in enhancing self-efficacy and, consequently, commitment to organizational change (Mangundjaya et al., 2023).

2.1 Collective efficacy

Collective efficacy refers to the shared belief among team members in their collective ability to overcome and master difficult tasks, crises, and hurdles together. When employees share this belief, they exhibit high confidence in their company's performance, fostering individual empowerment, collective self-confidence, and improved performance under

challenging conditions. This collective belief can be strengthened through positive experiences, role models, and experimenting with different methods (Bandura, 1998; Sutcliffe & Vogus, 2003; Bruch & Vogel, 2009).

Energizing and supportive leadership significantly boosts team performance, well-being, satisfaction, commitment, and family life of employees. Such leaders foster organizational performance, willingness to learn, innovation, and teamwork (Cameron & McNaughtan, 2014). When supervisors express positive emotions, they initiate a contagion effect, spreading similar emotions among employees (Bono & Illies, 2006).

Organizational self-efficacy, a form of collective efficacy, is crucial in decentralized, differentiated, and specialized organizations. High collective self-efficacy enables teams to coordinate effectively and tackle complex tasks, even when individual activities cannot be centrally controlled.

Key findings from recent studies underscore the importance of collective efficacy in various contexts. Hepler, Hill, Chase, and Feltz (2021) noted that collective efficacy in sports teams is crucial for successful performance. They found that collective efficacy is not merely the sum of individual self-efficacy but rather the team's shared belief in their ability to succeed together. This shared belief significantly impacts team cohesion, motivation, and overall performance.

Dharma and Parahyanti (2023) explored collective efficacy in virtual teams, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. They found that Paradoxical Leadership Behavior (PLB) and Perceived Organizational Support (POS) are critical antecedents of Virtual Team Collective Efficacy (VTCE). Their study revealed that leaders who can balance competing demands and provide substantial organizational support significantly enhance collective efficacy in remote working environments. PLB combines agentic and communal leadership, fostering an environment where employees feel supported and motivated to achieve team goals despite working remotely.

Additionally, research by Mangundjaya, Putri, and Shafira (2023) highlighted that effective change leadership positively influences team collective efficacy. Leaders who can inspire confidence, provide a clear vision, and foster a supportive environment contribute to higher collective efficacy, which is crucial for navigating organizational changes and achieving desired outcomes. Their findings indicate that psychological empowerment and change self-efficacy mediate the relationship between change leadership and affective commitment to change, enhancing the overall collective efficacy of the organization.

Moreover, collective efficacy can lead to better coping strategies, lower stress levels, and improved job satisfaction among employees. For instance, Fransen et al. (2017) found that collective efficacy in sports teams was associated with better emotional regulation, higher motivation, and improved performance, demonstrating the broad applicability of collective efficacy principles across different domains.

In conclusion, collective efficacy is vital for organizational success, especially in dynamic and complex environments. Strengthening collective efficacy through supportive leadership, positive experiences, and effective coordination can lead to enhanced team performance, innovation, and resilience. Organizations should focus on fostering a culture that supports collective efficacy to navigate challenges effectively and achieve sustainable growth.

2.2 How can this knowledge can now be used for the change process?

Change processes are often significant challenges for companies. However, if employees possess high self-efficacy, teams exhibit strong collective efficacy, and the organization demonstrates robust organizational efficacy, the likelihood of a successful change process increases. Strengthening these factors at various levels can enhance overall effectiveness and improve the chances of success during organizational change.

Research has shown that self-efficacy is positively related to successful organizational change. For instance, Saks and Ashforth (2000) found that employees with higher levels of self-efficacy are more likely to embrace change and participate actively in the change process. Similarly, Herscovitch and Meyer (2002) discovered that employees with high self-efficacy perceive change as a challenge rather than a threat and demonstrate greater commitment to the change process.

Moreover, self-efficacy mediates the relationship between leadership and organizational change. Liden, Wayne, Zhao, and Henderson (2008) found that transformational leadership enhances employee self-efficacy, which in turn boosts employee participation in organizational change. Leaders who instill a sense of self-efficacy in their employees are thus more effective in implementing change initiatives. This relationship underscores the importance of leadership styles that support and empower employees, fostering an environment where they feel capable and motivated to engage in change processes.

Several studies further support the role of self-efficacy in organizational change. For example, Karatepe (2013) demonstrated that employee self-efficacy is positively related

to their commitment to organizational change. Employees with high self-efficacy feel more capable of adapting to change and overcoming obstacles. Rafferty, Jimmieson, and Armenakis (2013) found that employee self-efficacy correlates positively with proactive behaviors during organizational change, such as seeking new information, identifying problems, and suggesting solutions. These proactive behaviors are essential for navigating the complexities of change and ensuring that employees contribute constructively to the transition.

Avey et al. (2009) found that employee self-efficacy is positively related to satisfaction with the change process, suggesting that employees with high self-efficacy feel more in control of their work environment and better cope with the stressors associated with change. This sense of control and competence reduces anxiety and resistance, fostering a more positive and collaborative atmosphere during transitions.

Organizations can support the development of self-efficacy in employees through training and development programs that build skills and knowledge related to the change initiative. Klassen and Chiu (2010) highlighted that training programs, providing necessary skills for navigating technology-based changes, led to increased self-efficacy. Social support and feedback also enhance self-efficacy. Bandura (1997) emphasized that social support and feedback can improve self-efficacy by offering performance improvement information and reassuring employees of their abilities. Mazzetti, Schaufeli, and Guglielmi (2014) provided evidence that supportive leadership behaviors, such as providing feedback and recognition, are positively associated with employee self-efficacy during change initiatives.

Creating a culture that supports risk-taking and experimentation is another effective approach. Anderson, Potocnik, and Zhou (2014) suggested that a culture of psychological safety, where employees feel comfortable taking risks and trying new approaches, can enhance self-efficacy by providing opportunities for learning and growth. A culture that values experimentation and views failure as a learning opportunity encourages employees to engage more fully with change initiatives, knowing they have the support to explore new methods and solutions.

Additionally, positive psychology interventions can play a crucial role in facilitating readiness for change. Shubina (2021) noted that interventions such as gratitude exercises, mindfulness practices, and strengths-based coaching can enhance psychological resilience and self-efficacy. These interventions help employees build the emotional and cognitive resources needed to navigate change effectively.

Furthermore, Amrollahifar and Yajie (2023) discussed how self-efficacy moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and work engagement, emphasizing that employees with higher self-efficacy can better manage their emotional responses and engage more effectively in their work. This finding is crucial for organizations aiming to enhance employee engagement during change processes.

Incorporating findings from Hepler et al. (2021), it is evident that collective efficacy, much like self-efficacy, plays a significant role in team dynamics and performance. Teams with high collective efficacy are more resilient and adaptable during change processes, which further strengthens the overall effectiveness of organizational change initiatives.

Organizations can foster self-efficacy in their employees through comprehensive strategies including training, social support, positive leadership, and a culture of psychological safety. By investing in self-efficacy, organizations can build a workforce that is better equipped and more willing to adapt to change, ultimately contributing to the success of organizational change initiatives.

3. Adaptability and Organizational Change

Adaptability refers to the ability of an individual or an organization to respond effectively to changes in the environment. Organizational change encompasses any alteration in an organization's structure, processes, or culture. Adaptability is a critical factor in organizational change because it enables organizations to respond effectively to change and maintain their competitiveness.

Recent research highlights the positive impact of adaptability on organizational change. For instance, the adaptability of employees significantly enhances the success of organizational change initiatives. Employees with high adaptability are more likely to embrace and support change, resulting in more effective implementation (Biçer, 2021). Additionally, organizations with a high level of adaptability are better equipped to respond to external pressures and market changes, leading to improved organizational performance (Biçer, 2021; Stouten et al., 2018).

Organizations can support the development of adaptability in their employees in several ways. One approach is to provide training programs focused on developing skills such as problem-solving, decision-making, and resilience. These programs equip employees with the necessary skills to respond effectively to changing circumstances. For example, training that enhances emotional intelligence and social skills can improve adaptability by helping employees manage stress and collaborate more effectively during change (Ainayya et

al., 2021). Creating a supportive organizational culture that values and rewards adaptability is another crucial approach. Encouraging employees to take risks, fostering a culture of experimentation, and recognizing and rewarding adaptability can enhance the overall adaptability of the workforce. The culture of an organization plays a significant role in how changes are perceived and accepted by employees. A strong, adaptive culture can facilitate smoother transitions and greater acceptance of new processes (Salsabila et al., 2021).

Further research by Faupel and Stüb (2019) indicates that transformational leadership positively influences employee adaptability. Leaders who inspire and motivate their teams can foster an environment where adaptability is valued and encouraged. This type of leadership supports employees through the uncertainties of change and helps them see change as an opportunity rather than a threat.

Additionally, the concept of an entrepreneurial mindset within organizations can significantly contribute to adaptability. Encouraging employees to think and act like entrepreneurs, taking ownership of their projects and seeking innovative solutions, can drive adaptability. This mindset enables employees to navigate changes proactively and leverage new opportunities for the organization (Niva et al., 2021).

Adaptability is not only about individual capabilities but also about how well an organization can integrate these capabilities into its processes and culture. Jacobs et al. (2013) emphasize the importance of a unified framework for organizational change that includes continuous improvement, innovation, and responsiveness to external and internal dynamics. Organizations that implement such frameworks can sustain agility and resilience in the face of change.

In the realm of digital transformation, adaptability is particularly crucial. The rapid pace of technological advancements necessitates that organizations remain flexible and responsive. Training employees to use new technologies effectively and fostering a culture that embraces technological change can enhance organizational adaptability. The ability to quickly adapt to new digital tools and processes is a key competitive advantage in today's business environment (Biçer, 2021).

Moreover, Ainayya et al. (2021) found that organizational culture and work motivation significantly influence employee job satisfaction, which is closely linked to adaptability. A motivated and satisfied workforce is more likely to exhibit adaptive behaviors, contributing to the overall success of change initiatives.

Organizations must also focus on developing adaptability at the leadership level. Leaders who are adaptable can model adaptive behaviors for their teams, creating a ripple effect throughout the organization. Leadership development programs that focus on adaptability and change management can prepare leaders to guide their organizations through complex changes (Cummings & Worley, 2014).

Positive psychology interventions (PPIs) can play a crucial role in facilitating readiness for change. Shubina (2021) noted that interventions such as gratitude exercises, mindfulness practices, and strengths-based coaching can enhance psychological resilience and self-efficacy. These interventions help employees build the emotional and cognitive resources needed to navigate change effectively.

Additionally, research by Mangundjaya, Putri, and Shafira (2023) emphasizes the importance of psychological empowerment and change self-efficacy as mediators between change leadership and affective commitment to change. Their study showed that while psychological empowerment did not significantly influence affective commitment, change self-efficacy did, highlighting its crucial role in change initiatives.

Moreover, Flores-Cabezas et al. (2020) found that organizations transitioning from rigid, vertical structures to more flexible, process-oriented structures could better meet changing customer demands. This shift not only improved adaptability but also increased the speed and efficiency of order fulfillment, which is critical in a dynamic market environment.

Adaptability plays a crucial role in organizational change, with recent research demonstrating its positive impact on organizational performance. Organizations can support the development of adaptability in their employees through training programs, fostering a supportive organizational culture, and encouraging an entrepreneurial mindset. By doing so, they can improve their ability to respond to change and maintain competitiveness in an increasingly dynamic environment.

4. Conclusion

Self-efficacy and adaptability are pivotal for successful organizational change. Self-efficacy enhances employees' motivation and commitment to change, fostering a proactive attitude toward overcoming challenges. Adaptability enables both individuals and organizations to respond effectively to changing environments, ensuring sustained competitiveness (Bandura, 1997; Biçer, 2021). The integration of these attributes into organizational practices can significantly enhance the success rates of change initiatives.

Recent studies have underscored the critical role of psychological empowerment and change self-efficacy as mediators in the relationship between change leadership and affective commitment to change. Mangundjaya, Putri, and Shafira (2023) found that while psychological empowerment alone may not significantly influence affective commitment, change self-efficacy does. This highlights the necessity of focusing on building self-efficacy in employees to foster a commitment to change. Additionally, research by Amrollahifar and Yajie (2023) demonstrates that self-efficacy moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and work engagement, further emphasizing its importance in change initiatives.

Positive psychology interventions (PPIs) have been identified as effective in enhancing employees' readiness for organizational change. Shubina (2021) emphasizes that interventions such as gratitude exercises, mindfulness practices, and strengths-based coaching can significantly boost psychological resilience and self-efficacy, preparing employees better for change. These interventions help in building a supportive and proactive organizational culture that values employee well-being and continuous improvement.

Research by Mohamed and Mohamed (2022) found that leaders' emotional intelligence significantly correlates with self-efficacy and resilience, which are crucial for navigating change effectively. Additionally, Salsabila et al. (2021) highlighted that a supportive organizational culture that rewards adaptability and creativity significantly improves employees' responsiveness to change.

5.1 Implications for Practice

Organizations aiming to enhance their adaptability and self-efficacy should consider implementing comprehensive training and development programs focused on problem-solving, decision-making, and emotional intelligence. These programs should aim at building resilience and collaboration skills, essential for navigating change (Ainayya et al., 2021). Training programs that improve emotional intelligence and social skills can also enhance employees' ability to manage stress and collaborate effectively during transitions (Mohamed & Mohamed, 2022).

Furthermore, fostering an organizational culture that rewards adaptability and creativity can significantly improve employees' responsiveness to change. This includes encouraging risk-taking and experimentation, as well as recognizing and rewarding adaptive behaviors (Salsabila et al., 2021). Leadership development programs should also be prioritized, as transformational leaders can effectively inspire

and motivate their teams, enhancing overall organizational adaptability (Faupel & Süß, 2019). Additionally, promoting an entrepreneurial mindset, as suggested by Niva et al. (2021), can empower employees to take initiative and drive innovation, further strengthening the organization's adaptability.

Positive psychology interventions should be integrated into organizational practices. For instance, implementing gratitude exercises, mindfulness practices, and strengths-based coaching can enhance psychological resilience and self-efficacy among employees (Shubina, 2021). These practices not only prepare employees for change but also contribute to their overall well-being and job satisfaction. Moreover, fostering a psychologically safe environment, where employees feel comfortable experimenting and taking risks, is crucial for cultivating adaptability and innovation. Flores-Cabezas et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of flexible organizational structures in adapting to changing market demands, underscoring the need for dynamic and responsive change strategies.

5.2 Implications for Further Research

Future research should continue to explore the complex relationship between self-efficacy, adaptability, and organizational change. Specifically, studies should focus on the effectiveness of various interventions aimed at enhancing self-efficacy and adaptability, and their impact on change outcomes. There is also a need to investigate how different contextual factors, such as organizational culture and leadership styles, influence the development of these attributes.

Longitudinal studies are particularly important to understand the long-term effects of these interventions on organizational change readiness and outcomes. Research should also aim to compare the effectiveness of different types of positive psychology interventions in facilitating readiness for organizational change (Shubina, 2021). Additionally, exploring the role of digital transformation in enhancing organizational adaptability and the integration of new technologies can provide valuable insights for contemporary organizations (Biçer, 2021).

Furthermore, examining the impact of emotional intelligence and resilience on the adaptability of both leaders and employees can provide a deeper understanding of how these factors interact to influence change outcomes (Mohamed & Mohamed, 2022). Investigating the dynamics of organizational structures, as highlighted by Flores-Cabezas et al. (2020), and their role in supporting adaptive behaviors, can also contribute to the development of more effective change

strategies. Additionally, research by Hutabarat, Devany, and Manurung (2021) indicates that readiness for digital transformation is crucial for maintaining competitive advantage, which necessitates further exploration of digital readiness in the context of organizational change.

5.3 Limitations of this Study

This study has several limitations. First, the reliance on self-reported data may introduce bias, as participants might respond in a socially desirable manner. Future research should incorporate a mixed-methods approach, including qualitative data and observational studies, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing organizational change.

Second, the study's cross-sectional design limits the ability to draw causal inferences. Longitudinal studies are needed to establish causal relationships between self-efficacy, adaptability, and successful organizational change. Third, the study's generalizability is limited by the specific organizational contexts examined. Future research should include a diverse range of organizations across different industries to enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Lastly, while this study focuses on positive psychology interventions and their impact on organizational change, it does not fully explore the potential negative outcomes or resistance that might arise. Understanding the dual nature of these interventions and their effects on various organizational dynamics is crucial for developing more holistic and effective change strategies (Flores-Cabezas et al., 2020). Additionally, future studies should consider the role of leadership styles and their influence on adaptability and self-efficacy in different organizational settings.

Statement of Compliance

We, the authors of this manuscript, hereby declare that our work on the study has been conducted with complete independence and integrity. We affirm that there are no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise, that could have influenced the outcomes or interpretations presented in this research. Both authors have independently contributed to the research, analysis, and writing of this manuscript. Our roles and contributions have been solely driven by academic and professional standards without external influence.

We declare that there are no personal, professional, or financial relationships that could be perceived as influencing the research. Neither author has received any benefits or advantages that could create a bias in the study's design, results, or conclusions.

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No external funding sources have been used, ensuring that the research has been conducted without any undue influence from outside entities.

We are committed to maintaining the highest standards of academic integrity and transparency. Our findings and conclusions are the result of unbiased scientific inquiry aimed at advancing the understanding of Adaptability and Self-Efficacy.

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